

THE IMPACT OF CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT ON THE POST-PANDEMIC EDUCATION PROCESS. A CASE STUDY FROM A ROMANIAN PRE-UNIVERSITY SCHOOLS

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Abstract

Purpose – *The article aims to examine classroom management in specific traditional learning spaces as one of the disruptive factors of the post-pandemic educational process. This reduces the attraction of educational facilities. Comparing cases from theoretical and technological classrooms will provide more realistic evidence of the phenomenon studied.*

Methodology/approach – *Based on short reviews of the literature on Romania's pre-university education system and real observations of two different secondary schools, and based on questionnaires, a survey was developed. The main objective is to provide information, opinions, and figures on the role of classroom management in post-pandemic education.*

Findings - *Respondents were satisfied with physical learning spaces, ambient environments, furniture, lighting, air, and sound quality. Teachers and students used technology and devices under appropriate conditions. Ergonomics can be a solution to improving work and learning conditions.*

Research limitations/implications – *The research sample consists of 66 respondents from two classes of two branches: one technological and one theoretical, in Romania.*

Practical implications - *School managers, local and national policy makers must develop visions that integrate space, technology, and education quality standards. Teachers' health and safety at work should be more emphasized. STEM education should be better supported with modern didactic materials.*

Originality/value – *This research approach has been designed and applied in an innovative way, as no other similar study has been identified in the literature.*

Key words: *Pre-university education, learning space, STEM education.*

Introduction

In 1925, the Minister of Public Instruction, Constantin Angelescu, decided to create in Romania a new method of examination called the Baccalaureate. His entire activity went in three directions: unification of the education system, building new schools, and raising the status of the teaching staff (Panaitescu, 1928; Petrica, 2010). Since then, the Romanian education system has followed different strategic plans and recently aligned with the standards of education in the European system. Thus, in almost 100 years, it seems that the Romanian education system has suffered a dynamic transformation, being, in the last two years, affected by the Covid-19 pandemic crisis, which has accelerated the digital transformations of all processes. Students and teachers experienced uncertainty and stressful situations; communication and feedback during the education process were negatively affected, and some pupils, students lost their connection with the group of learners, with schools, colleges or universities. The main cause of this phenomenon was a lack of digital competence in teachers and students, accompanied by the lack of methods (including teacher methods) and tools (with reference to equipment and software) for online learning (lack of organization of new methods of evaluation of teaching and learning).

Additionally, the labor market has been affected in the last two years. The way of work has evolved (online, work-from-home, hybrid, etc.), the expectations of employees and employers have changed,

and the number of jobs available has been different distributed by industries. Two years ago, candidates complained that there were not enough jobs. Now, employers complain about the lack of candidates. Although the dynamics of the labor market depends on industry, the services sector is the most affected and the production and transportation sectors are fewer.

In Romania, according to official statistical data provided by the National Trade Register Office (ONRC), regarding companies with foreign capital participation (<https://www.onrc.ro/index.php/ro/statistici?id=254>), the National Institute of Statistics (INS), regarding the average number of employees by counties, (<http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/#/pages/tables/insse-table>), and the National Bank of Romania (BNR), regarding Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) (<https://www.bnr.ro/PublicationDocuments.aspx?icid=14364>), and the synthesis in Table 1, in the current economic environment, FDI and labor migration directly affect the reduction in workforce (see county relationships). The trends of the three indicators allow us to observe discrepancies between Romanian counties that determine the richness and poverty of the development region.

Table 1. Romania's 2020 statistics (BNR, ONRC, INS, 2022)

County	FDI balance Million Euro (BNR, 2022)	Total turnover Billion Lei (ONRC, 2022)	Average number of employees (INS, 2022)
Bucharest	48,713	637	1,133,007
Ilfov	5,876	121	187,011
Timis	4,579	74	198,914
Brasov	2,668	53	146,464
Prahova	2,579	60	142,238
Cluj	2,101	72	202,031
Mureş	1,884	35	93,398
Sibiu	1,820	38	108,64
Constanta	1,804	48	127,727
Arges	1,521	61	134,542
Dolj	1,334	38	93,892
Arad	1,103	31	84,333
Alba	1,024	28	63,096
Bihor	1,023	39	120,133
Olt	904	16	43,636
Maramures	710	20	78,102
Galaţi	708	27	75,648
Satu Mare	570	20	58,431
Iasi	515	32	111,854
Hunedoara	456	13	60,445
Buzau	451	19	54,207
Salaj	451	8	28,752
Dambovita	442	17	51,288
Suceava	420	22	70,075
Giurgiu	363	8	26,657
Ialomita	333	9	25,197
Bacău	329	32	82,652
Calarasi	299	8	25,386
Tulcea	295	9	29,314
Covasna	283	7	26,677
Harghita	223	12	48,305
Caras-Severin	216	6	30,097

Braila	199	9	37,073
Neamt	193	13	48,101
Valcea	183	13	49,730
Bistrita-Nasaud	123	13	47,658
Vrancea	120	10	37,243
Teleorman	117	7	27,523
Botosani	74	8	30,327
Vaslui	58	7	30,490
Mehedinti	14	4	16,867
Gorj	5	8	45,277

For the first quarter of 2022 (Eurostat Statistics Explained, 2022), the employment rate of the working-age population, between 20 and 64 years, was 74.5 percent, showing the labor market volatility. However, after lifting Covid-19 restrictions, the appearances of the Ukrainian war, the global disruptions in supply chains that have led to inflation acceleration, candidates' manifest cautiousness in job searches. The "chase for employees" is the new phenomenon on the labor market. During and after the pandemic crisis, many studies described these problems (Demyen and Ciurea, 2018; Radu, 2018; Russu, 2018; Russu, 2019; Taicu, 2019; Maita, Padurean, and Apostol, 2021; Plesca et al., 2021).

During the period of the Pandemic Crisis, it has been observed that pre-education systems most commonly use old classroom learning spaces, which sometimes pose a risk to both teachers and learners; learning motivation of students is negatively affected. These facts and phenomena were discovered through observation and intense discussions among teachers after returning to the face-to-face education style. Thus, teaching staff complained that learning spaces are stressful (Marin, 2022). Other risks have been identified as those associated with online and/or hybrid teaching conditions, such as technical problems, symptoms of depression, and burnout. In 2021, teachers reported much higher levels of stress and symptoms related to their work than the general population (Schipor and Duca, 2021; Alexescu et al., 2022; Ciuhan, Nicolau and Iliescu, 2022).

Consequently, the 2021 National Report on Pre-university Education published by the Romanian Ministry of Education showed that of the total 2,500,000 schoolchildren, more than 285,000 (aged between 7 and 17 years old) were out of school, of which more than 20,000 from the primary and secondary school system, and about 14,000 high school students. In the last three years of high school education, the dropout rate was a constant value (2.5 percent).

In this complex and dynamic context, the present article aims to examine classroom management in specific traditional learning spaces as one of the disruptive factors of the post-pandemic educational process, which reduces the attractiveness of the educational process locations. Comparisons between the branches of the theoretical and technological schools provide solid arguments on the phenomena studied.

Methodology

Based on a brief literature review related to the pre-university education system in Romania, and real-life observations in two different high schools, have been built an applicative research methodology using a survey based on a questionnaire. The main objective was to provide insights, opinions and figures about the role played by the classroom management in the post-pandemic education process. According to Oxford Bibliography: "Classroom management can be defined as the actions teachers take to establish and sustain an environment that fosters students' academic achievement as well as their social, emotional, and moral growth". The general goal in this case is to rich balance for a type of order that facilitate the learning, communication, interaction processes related to the education process¹. Classroom management uses different methods and tools (including software and hardware) that facilitate the learning process and knowledge acquisition (to support a student-centered approach). In this context, the learning space, together with all visual representations, displays, or other learning tools

¹ Retrieved from: <https://www.oxfordbibliographies.com/view/document/obo-9780199756810/obo-9780199756810-0155.xml> (Access 29-07-2022)

(schema, circuits, figures, drawings, pictures), could facilitate or inhibit the creative processes associated with learning.

Considering this second directive of the 1919 document "Goals of the Minister of Instruction" (available at the Romanian Academy Library), on school buildings and their construction, and the present learning spaces, we created a survey to characterize the relationship between learning spaces (buildings and physical resources) and the learning process. The survey has been applied in the case of two classes of pre-university system: one from a theoretical branch classroom and one from the technological branch (both high schools were from the West Development Region of Romania). Table 2 shows the use of the questionnaire for research.

Table 2. Questionnaire for examining and evaluating the use of learning spaces

Each school needs visions and developmental strategies that are essentially designed to determine the relationship between these concepts: the development of buildings and physical resources, as well as learning. Schools must develop visions that combine space, technology, and education. Sustainable development must also continue.

Although there are not enough facilities in all classrooms, communicating and sharing your vision with school staff is important to provide everyone with the opportunity to look at how to improve education and learning.

Schools recognize that classrooms should not be static. Modern furniture allows one to adapt the classroom to learn activities. Schools must consider the reuse of furniture in new designs. The two main points to be considered are technology and the teaching approach of teachers and students. Virtual spaces are not merely physical classrooms.

The following questions will help explore and determine how to use learning spaces, and the following lists will serve as a starting point for each space.

1. Does the space have different learning themes?
 2. Is there enough room to accommodate?
 3. Can the space be used during the lesson?
 4. Can the space be used before and after the lesson?
 5. Is the furniture flexible and mobile?
 6. Is the lighting adjustable and adequate for teaching and learning?
 7. Is the acoustic suitable for the activities carried out?
 8. Is the air quality adequate for the activities carried out?
 9. Is the space accessible?
 10. Does the teacher move regularly around the perimeter of the classroom / space?
 11. Do students travel through the classroom during the lesson to perform various tasks?
 12. Does the teacher prepare various tasks for different students?
 13. Do students produce the same learning outcomes?
 14. Students are expected to complete tasks based on technology, before the class?
 15. Do students use technology during lessons?
 16. Can students use their own devices during the lesson?
 17. Does the teacher use technology during the lesson?
 18. The program gives students the flexibility to decide when and where to study.
 19. Is the space occupied daily?
 20. Please express your opinion on this possible "ergonomic class of the future"
- (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Question 20. The case of the possible "ergonomic class of the future"

The results achieved from the survey have been interpreted based on informal discussions with learners and practical observations in the two classes (Figures 2a, 2b, 2c, 2d, 3a, 3b, 3c). Furthermore, to better understand the results, a brief analysis was developed with the high school directors and additional modern ergonomic learning space solutions were considered.

Results

Of the total of 66 responses, 21 were from teachers/managers and 45 from learners. Students in the technological branch of the high schools were forestry, environmental protection and mechanics, and those from the high school were vocational, theological. The passing rate of the baccalaureate exam for the period 2018 - 2020 of the theoretical high school is 100 percent, and for the one of technological branch, it does not exceed 50 percent for the same period.

Only the theoretical high school has been energetically rehabilitated in 2020. Questions about the physical learning space, the ambient environment, respectively, the furnishing, lighting, air quality and acoustics, and movement of the participants to the lessons inside the space received positive responses, 46 to 55 percent of respondents agree on 'good' and 'very good' conditions in their classes. Regarding the technology and devices used by both teachers and students during lessons, 38 to 42 percent of the respondents agreed on adequate conditions.

However, in the case of Question 13 (see Table 2) related to the learning outcomes different opinions have been collected: 6.08 percent totally disagree; 33.33 percent disagree; 31.81 percent neither agree/disagree; 25.75 percent agree; 3.03 percent totally agree. These results should be interpreted with the answers to question 20, related to users' opinions of the users about the ergonomic class solution (Figure 1). We draw attention to the following responses (only the third is from the theoretical branch of high school):

1. "With involvement and respect for the actors on the education scene, it could also be possible here. Flexibility, mobility, and modernity are the keys to success. The atmosphere changes, communication barriers and blockages disappear in such a classroom.
2. It is a room where students would probably like to come to the respective school and besides that they would learn much more than they usually do.
3. It seems to me to be a friendly, well-equipped, and arranged environment where you can come with love.
4. I think this class would be useful for students to relax during school.
5. It looks incredible, it would be great if we had a class like that, but with the education system and the allocated budget, we dreamed of something for nothing.

a. General view of the classroom

b. Posters on the classroom's wall

c. Motivational poster

d. The front of the classroom - the teachers' view

Figure 2. The case of the classroom from the theoretical branch.

a. General view of the classroom with didactic materials on the walls, since 1984

b. Didactic material - Schema of a circuit from 1984

c. Didactic material - Engine from 1984

Figure 3. The case of the classroom from the technologic branch.

6. It is a step forward, but the system problem comes from teachers with airs of superiority and bored with life, and such a teacher has no business in the department.
7. Well calibrated, it offers optimal positioning of students for constructive interaction. Provides physical and emotional comfort”.

Furthermore, the teachers' responses that were most relevant to the study results are:

1. “The classroom has mobile furniture that favors the arrangement of various activities, has modern technical means, the only improvement would be natural lighting and the existence of a more generous space, which would allow for the free movement of students and teaching staff.

2. I prefer a quieter space with a theme area and a relaxation/break area. The space in the picture looks suffocating. I would keep the equipment: video projector, resources. I prefer the flexibility of the furniture positioning if needed, for example, I prefer the U shape.
3. I think this room is ergonomic from all points of view, and the arrangement is designed not only for classroom use, but also as a multimedia room, a conference room or even offices”.

Discussions and Conclusions

The schools / high schools of the preuniversity system should be the main targets of the Romanian municipality’s renovation strategies, and their energy rehabilitation should be a national priority. They have a long-term impact on social development, including financial, environmental, and on the health and education performance of teaching staff and learners (children, students).

To involve students in authentic and meaningful learning situations, including design, implementation, testing, reflection, and documentation, there is also a strong need to equip the learning spaces with adequate visual and didactic materials related to the specialty (theoretical or technological branches).

Special attention should be paid to STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics), which needs modern didactical and pedagogical materials and tools. These fields are of great interest to children and students. In addition, experts, local stakeholders, and representatives of the labor market can support a wide range of educational topics.

Moving to the implementation phase is more difficult and not risk-free. The success of education is not only associated with identifying and satisfying learning needs. However, it is necessary to form a multidisciplinary team to lay the foundations for innovation in STEM education. School managers should also collect data on the working conditions of teachers and the conditions of health and safety at work. Policy makers, local and national stakeholders should work together to develop a clear policy on blended/online education based on clear and comprehensive technical standards.

Notes

The photos were taken with the consent of all participants involved in completing the survey questionnaire.

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